

A Hospital Based Observational Study Evaluating the Outcomes of Primary Angioplasty in Myocardial Infarction in Diabetics and Non-Diabetics

Mukesh Shandilya¹, Ravivishnu Prasad²

¹Senior Resident (Academic) Department of Cardiology, IGIMS, PATNA, Bihar, India

²Additional Professor, Department of Cardiology, IGIMS, PATNA, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Mukesh Shandilya

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess the outcomes of primary angioplasty in myocardial infarction as a comparison between diabetics and non-diabetics.

Methods: The present study was conducted in the Department of Cardiology, IGIMS, PATNA, Bihar for the period of one year. 100 patients were included in the diabetic group and 100 subjects in the non-diabetic group.

Results: Diabetic patients had worse cardiac risk factor profiles and initial presentation characteristics. Left ventricular ejection fraction was lower and multivessel disease (>50% diameter stenosis in ≥ 2 coronary arteries) was more common in diabetics. However, diabetic subjects had a higher incidence of TIMI flow ≥ 2 before PCI. Fewer diabetic than nondiabetic patients underwent primary PCI. Diabetics who underwent PCI were more likely to have baseline TIMI flow ≤ 1 but otherwise had similar baseline clinical and angiographic characteristics as diabetics who did not undergo PCI. Bypass surgery during the initial hospitalization was performed more frequently in diabetics. The 2 groups were similar with respect to maximum balloon diameter (an indicator of vessel diameter), use of stents and intravenous abciximab and final stenosis and TIMI flow. Diabetics who had primary PCI had higher in-hospital mortality than nondiabetics who had PCI. At 6-month follow-up, diabetics who underwent primary PCI had higher incidences of death and tended to have higher MACE rates, but also had similar reinfarction and ischemia-driven TVR rates as nondiabetics who underwent primary PCI.

Conclusion: We concluded that diabetics with AMI have less favorable baseline characteristics and are less likely to undergo primary PCI than nondiabetics. Despite excellent angiographic results, diabetics had significantly worse 6-month mortality.

Keywords: Outcomes, Primary Angioplasty, Myocardial Infarction, Diabetics, Non-Diabetics.

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Introduction

The relation between diabetes and coronary artery disease is marked by two circumstances: the high incidence of coronary artery disease in diabetic patients and its poor prognosis in diabetics compared to non-diabetics. It is estimated that more than 50% of adult diabetics have significant coronary atherosclerosis, a prevalence 10 times greater than that of the general population, which is about 2%-4%. [1-3] In fact, at present diabetes is considered not only a risk factor, but also a marker of cardiovascular disease from the point of view of prevention. Consequently, the recommended prevention interventions are the same for diabetics as for patients with coronary artery disease. [3,4] Diabetes not only increases the incidence of coronary disease, but also contributes to a less favorable prognosis. Thus, cardiovascular mortality

is twice as frequent in diabetic men and four times as frequent in diabetic women. In general, if we analyze any subgroup of diabetics with coronary artery disease, they have a worse long-term clinical evolution in terms of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. [2,3]

Patients with diabetes mellitus (DM) and acute myocardial infarction (AMI) are at high risk for recurrent cardiovascular events [5,6], in part due to a greater tendency towards thrombosis. [7,8] Diabetics are characterized by increased platelet reactivity [9] including higher reactivity while on antiplatelet treatment. [10,11] ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) is characterized by a highly prothrombotic state [12], the highest of which can be observed in diabetic STEMI patients. [13]

Primary percutaneous coronary intervention (pPCI) is the most effective and most recommended therapeutic approach in patients with STEMI and in those at very high-risk myocardial infarction without persistent ST-segment elevation (non-STEMI with ongoing ischemia). [14] Prasugrel and ticagrelor are the currently recommended treatment in patients with acute coronary syndromes, including STEMI, since they have been shown to reduce ischemic events compared to clopidogrel. [15]

The aim of the present study was to assess the outcomes of primary angioplasty in myocardial infarction as a comparison between diabetics and non-diabetics.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Cardiology, IGIMS, PATNA, Bihar for the period of one year. 100 patients were included in the diabetic group and 100 subjects in the non-diabetic group.

Patients were included if they were ≥ 18 years old, if symptoms of myocardial infarction had begun < 12 hours before written informed consent was requested, and if they had either ST-segment elevation of ≥ 1 mm in ≥ 2 contiguous leads or a non diagnostic electrocardiogram (including left bundle branch block, a paced rhythm, ST-segment depression, or T-wave inversion) with documentation of AMI in the catheterization laboratory (i.e., high-grade coronary stenosis and associated left ventricular wall motion abnormalities). Clinical criteria for exclusion were previous administration of thrombolytic agents for the index infarction, current use of warfarin, stroke during the previous month, renal failure, cardiogenic shock, remaining life expectancy of < 1 year, childbearing potential (unless the result of a recent pregnancy test was negative), and known contraindications to aspirin or heparin, or contraindications to ticlopidine in later PAMI studies. [16-18] Informed consent was obtained from all patients by the study investigators or coordinators at their respective institutions.

Data collection and comparisons: For each of the clinical trials, research nurses or coordinators at each site collected data prospectively and completed detailed case report forms. Independent data monitors traveled to the participating sites to verify hospital records for all patients. Cineangiograms, obtained at the time of the acute coronary intervention, were analyzed by the individual operators and subsequently by core laboratories, to assess coronary anatomy, estimate Thrombolysis In Myocardial Infarction (TIMI) flow grades, percentage diameter stenosis, left ventricular ejection fraction, and angiographic outcomes of intervention.

We compared baseline clinical, demographic, and angiographic characteristics (TIMI flow, diameter stenosis, location of infarct-related artery, and multivessel disease) between diabetic and nondiabetic patients. We also compared angiographic outcomes (TIMI flow and diameter stenosis after percutaneous coronary intervention [PCI]), maximum balloon diameter, and utilization of stents and intravenous abciximab between the groups. Core laboratory data were considered incomplete for left ventricular ejection fraction and initial TIMI flow grade; therefore, operator-defined data were used for these variables.

Study end-points and definitions: The primary study outcomes included in-hospital mortality, 6-month mortality, and 6-month incidence of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACEs), defined as death, or reinfarction, or ischemia-driven target vessel revascularization (TVR). Reinfarction was defined as recurrent clinical symptoms (or the development of new electrocardiographic changes) accompanied by new elevation of creatine kinase and creatine kinase-MB enzyme levels. Ischemia-driven TVR was defined as TVR (either PCI or bypass surgery) prompted by symptoms or objective evidence of ischemia.

The incidence of in-hospital complications (pulmonary edema, dialysis, sustained hypotension, cardiopulmonary resuscitation, disabling stroke, reinfarction, and ischemic TVR) and need for coronary artery bypass graft surgery were also compared between the 2 groups. Sustained hypotension was defined as systolic blood pressure < 80 mm Hg unresponsive to intravenous fluids, requiring pressors for > 1 hour or intra-aortic balloon pump.

Statistical analysis: All categorical variables are expressed as percentages and continuous variables as mean ± 1 SD. We used the chi-square test or Fisher's 2-sided exact test for comparisons of categorical variables, and the Wilcoxon rank test for comparisons of continuous variables. For comparison of cumulative 6-month mortality rates between the 2 groups, we used Kaplan-Meier survival analysis and the log-rank test. To assess the independent effect of a history of diabetes on in-hospital and 6-month outcomes, we performed multivariate analyses using Cox proportional hazards regression (for 6-month mortality) or step-down multiple logistic regression (for other clinical outcomes that showed an univariate association with diabetes [$p < 0.05$]). Baseline clinical and angiographic variables that showed a significant or borderline univariate association ($p < 0.10$) with a history of diabetes were included in the multivariate analyses. Adjusted odds ratios (ORs) (or hazard ratios) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated for each variable in the final

model. History of diabetes mellitus remained in these models, irrespective of its significance.

Results

Table 1: Baseline Clinical Characteristics

Variables	Diabetic group (n = 100)	Non-diabetic group 0 (n = 100)	p Value
Age (years) Women	62 ± 12	58 ± 10	<0.0001
Systemic hypertension Peripheral vascular disease	40%	28%	<0.0001
Current smoker	65%	41%	<0.0001
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	15%	7%	<0.0001
Dyslipidemia	30%	44%	<0.0001
Cerebrovascular accident Prior angina pectoris	7%	4%	0.22
Prior myocardial infarction Prior PCI	44%	40%	0.18
Prior heart failure	9%	5%	<0.0001
Prior coronary artery bypass grafting	22%	18%	0.075
Initial presentation Killip class ≥2	22%	15%	<0.0001
Heart rate (beats/min) Heart rate >100 beats/min	16%	9%	<0.0001
Systolic blood pressure (mm Hg) Systolic blood pressure <100 mm Hg†	6%	2%	<0.0001
Aspirin before intervention	8%	5%	0.003
Intravenous heparin before intervention	17%	13%	0.007
Time from symptom onset to arrival at emergency department (min)	90 ± 18	88 ± 22	<0.0001
Time from arrival at emergency department to balloon inflation (min)	25%	22%	0.062
	117 ± 23	112 ± 28	0.001
	28%	34%	0.020
	90%	89%	0.840
	82%	85%	0.066
	174 ± 166	158 ± 176	0.044
	162 ± 220	138 ± 140	0.0005

Diabetic patients had worse cardiac risk factor profiles and initial presentation characteristics.

Table 2: Angiographic Characteristics

	Diabetic group	Non-diabetic group	p Value
Baseline angiographic characteristics Ejection fraction (%)	46 ± 14	49 ± 11	0.0046
TIMI flow before intervention 0-1	70%	75%	0.0007
2-3	30%	25%	
Infarct-related coronary artery Left anterior descending Right	44%	42%	0.78
Left circumflex Multivessel disease	42%	43%	0.64
Underwent PCI	15%	15%	0.76
PCI characteristics	62%	48%	<0.0001
Maximum balloon size (mm)§	87%	90%	0.007
Stent implantation Intravenous abciximab	3.2 ± 0.5	3.2 ± 0.5	0.70
Final TIMI 3 flow	32	35	0.24
Final diameter stenosis (%)	9.8%	9.2%	0.70
	94%	95%	0.60
	20 ± 16	20 ± 16	0.96

Left ventricular ejection fraction was lower and multivessel disease (>50% diameter stenosis in ≥2 coronary arteries) was more common in diabetics. However, diabetic subjects had a higher incidence of TIMI flow ≥2 before PCI. Fewer diabetic than nondiabetic patients underwent primary PCI. Diabetics who underwent PCI were more likely to have baseline TIMI flow ≤1 but otherwise had

similar baseline clinical and angiographic characteristics as diabetics who did not undergo PCI. Bypass surgery during the initial hospitalization was performed more frequently in diabetics. The 2 groups were similar with respect to maximum balloon diameter (an indicator of vessel diameter), use of stents and intravenous abciximab and final stenosis and TIMI flow.

Table 3: Six-Month Outcomes

6-Months Outcomes	Diabetes Mellitus		Unadjusted Hazard Ratio	p Value
	Present	Absent		
Intention-to-treat analysis				
Death	9%	4%	1.94	<0.0001
MACE	18%	15%	1.25	0.032
Reinfarction	4%	3%	1.20	0.42
I-TVR	8%	10%	0.84	0.20
Subset analysis of patients who had				
PCI	7%	4%	1.86	0.0003
Death	18%	16%	1.22	0.07
MACE	4%	3%	1.18	0.50
Reinfarction I-TVR	9%	12%	0.88	0.36

Diabetics who had primary PCI had higher in-hospital mortality than nondiabetics who had PCI. At 6-month follow-up, diabetics who underwent primary PCI had higher incidences of death and tended to have higher MACE rates, but also had similar reinfarction and ischemia-driven TVR rates as nondiabetics who underwent primary PCI.

Discussion

Although thrombolytic therapy has improved outcomes among diabetics with AMI [19], their outcomes remain unacceptably poor. The underlying mechanisms for these poor outcomes are not clearly understood; diabetics undergoing thrombolysis in the Global Utilization of Streptokinase and TPA (alteplase) for Occluded Coronary Arteries (GUSTO-I) study had similarly-sized or smaller infarctions compared with nondiabetics, similar 90-min patency rates, comparable 30-day reinfarction rates and equivalent left ventricular systolic function, yet their adjusted 30-day mortality was significantly higher. [20]

Primary angioplasty is an alternative strategy to achieve reperfusion in AMI [21], but the effect of diabetic status on angiographic and clinical outcomes of this strategy have not been well documented. Primary angioplasty may be less successful among diabetics owing to the more extensive atherosclerosis, impaired microvascular autoregulation and prothrombotic and vasospastic effects of diabetes. [22,23] Diabetic patients had worse cardiac risk factor profiles and initial presentation characteristics. Left ventricular ejection fraction was lower and multivessel disease (>50% diameter stenosis in ≥ 2 coronary arteries) was more common in diabetics. However, diabetic subjects had a higher incidence of TIMI flow ≥ 2 before PCI. Fewer diabetic than nondiabetic patients underwent primary PCI. Diabetics who underwent PCI were more likely to have baseline TIMI flow ≤ 1 but otherwise had similar baseline clinical and angiographic characteristics as diabetics who did not undergo PCI. Bypass surgery during the initial hospitalization was performed more frequently in diabetics.

The 2 groups were similar with respect to maximum balloon diameter (an indicator of vessel diameter), use of stents and intravenous abciximab and final stenosis and TIMI flow. Diabetics who had primary PCI had higher in-hospital mortality than nondiabetics who had PCI. At 6-month follow-up, diabetics who underwent primary PCI had higher incidences of death and tended to have higher MACE rates, but also had similar reinfarction and ischemia-driven TVR rates as nondiabetics who underwent primary PCI. Consistent with prior studies [24-26] we found that patients with diabetes who had AMI had worse base-line clinical characteristics, such as older age and later presentation, were more likely to be women, and had higher atherosclerotic burden (i.e., higher incidence of peripheral vascular disease, prior cerebrovascular accident, myocardial infarction, PCI, or coronary artery bypass graft surgery, and multivessel coronary disease). Unlike 1 angiographic study that showed more severe stenosis and poorer flow in the infarct-related artery [27], diabetics in our study had better baseline TIMI flow than nondiabetics. Given the similar utilization of adjunctive medical therapy— aspirin, intravenous heparin, and abciximab— between the groups, this finding is surprising. It is possible that the longer time from chest pain onset to treatment in diabetics allowed more endogenous reperfusion, and thus better baseline TIMI flow. Alternatively, one could argue that this finding reflects selection bias, because diabetic patients with poor TIMI flow may have been excluded because of cardiogenic shock at presentation or death before arrival to the hospital.

Conclusion

We concluded that diabetics with AMI have less favorable baseline characteristics and are less likely to undergo primary PCI than nondiabetics. Despite excellent angiographic results, diabetics had significantly worse 6-month mortality.

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